

METHODS OF FORMING COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN NON-TRADITIONAL FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Annotation. *The existence of mankind is unthinkable outside of communicative activity. Regardless of gender, age, education, social status, territorial and national affiliation, and many other data that characterize a human personality, we constantly request, transmit and store information. We are actively engaged in communication activities.*

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The formation of an active personality is impossible without the activity in mastering knowledge. Much here depends on the skill of the teacher, on his ability to organize the educational process, on his creativity and the constant search for new forms and techniques of learning. The pedagogical creativity of the teacher, freed from the template, creates interesting examples of non-standard forms of education, which allows him to return the lost interest in learning a foreign language. Neither the program, nor the textbook, nor the methodological manual can provide the teacher with a ready-made lesson scheme. He must design it himself, taking into account the learning conditions and the composition of students. "At the same time, the analysis of the current system for organizing the study of foreign languages shows that educational standards, curricula and textbooks do not fully meet modern requirements, especially in terms of the use of advanced information and media technologies. Training is conducted mainly by traditional methods..." emphasized in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" of December 10, 2012 NI-1875. Therefore, the teacher

needs to move away from the standard lesson to some extent, introduce something new that could attract attention, activate the activities of students, make them think, search, act.

A non-traditional lesson is an improvisation of a lesson that has a non-traditional structure. Such a lesson includes techniques and methods of various forms of education. It is based on the joint activities of teachers and students, joint search, testing of new forms of work, which ultimately affects the activation of cognitive activity of students in the classroom and the improvement of teaching efficiency. Among the large number of non-traditional lessons are the following: lessons - business or role-playing games, lessons - press conferences, lessons-competitions, lessons such as KVN, lessons with group forms of work, lessons-games, lessons-holidays, etc.

It is not necessary that the whole lesson should become non-traditional, it is possible to insert in it certain elements that are aim at activating learning. Computer technologies and project methods, non- standard forms of testing, etc. The purpose of non-traditional lessons is to work out new methods, forms, techniques and means of learning, which leads to the implementation of the basic law of pedagogy - the law on learning activity.

As practice shows, non-traditional forms of education

Assume:

- use of collective forms of work;
- instilling interest in the subject;
- development of skills and abilities for independent work;
- intensification of students' activities;
- when preparing for the lesson, students themselves look for interesting material;
- fuller implementation of practical, educational, Educational and developmental learning goals.

The content, organization and conduct of a foreign language lesson determine the strength of the impact on students of the educational process.

Mastery of the language is carried out primarily in class.

A modern foreign language lesson is a complex education.

Preparing and conducting it require a lot of creative effort from the teacher.

First, multifaceted tasks are solved in the lesson. In each lesson, students should get everything they need for practical knowledge of the language being studied. It can be expressed in a better understanding of speech by ear by mastering new words, a new grammatical form, structure; in acquiring knowledge about the culture of the country of the language being studied in the field of literature, music, history, that is, students are immersed in the national culture and national psychology of the country of the language being studied.

Lesson material and means

To activate it, you should

To use for educational purposes. The teacher decides what exactly should be brought up in the student in this lesson, using techniques and methods for their emotional and intellectual development.

Secondly, during the lesson, it ensures the active cognitive activity of students, using various forms of its organization: frontal, collective and individual.

The frontal form of organization of students' educational activities in the classroom contributes to the establishment of a particularly close relationship between the teacher and the class, joint friendly work of students, during which general participation is achieved in solving not only educational, but also educational problems, mutual assistance, the formation of sustainable cognitive interests, allows the use of a variety of methods and techniques to activate the learning process. This form ensures the involvement of all students in the work of the audience and their overall progress in learning.

At the same time, it cannot be universal, as it does not sufficiently take into account the level of development, cognitive interests and opportunities, specific characteristics of each student. Therefore

Frontal work in class is combined with individual work. Thus, along with the frontal presentation of the material by the teacher, which is most often used to report new information, frontal conversation is widely used. By raising questions (problem, leading, etc.), comments and evaluative judgments, he directs the course of the conversation in such a way as to involve individual students in the collective discussion, taking into account their individual characteristics. Frontal learning work can also be organized in such a way that each student performs a task or exercise independently, simultaneously with others, on the instructions and under the guidance of a teacher. Individual tasks can be part of the overall collective task, and after they are completed, all students take part in the discussion of the results obtained.

The individual form of educational work in the classroom is characterized by a high level of independence of students. Its advantages are that learning corresponds to the maximum degree of development, abilities and cognitive capabilities of each student. The individual form of work is most appropriate when performing various exercises and solving problems, it is successfully used in programmable learning, when learning foreign languages in language laboratories, as well as to deepen knowledge and fill the gaps of students in the study of the material, in the formation of skills.

The individual form of work of students in the lesson allows you to regulate the pace of progress in the teaching of each of them, in accordance with its preparation and capabilities. Its success is determined by the correct selection of differentiated tasks, systematic control of the teacher over their implementation, the provision of timely assistance in solving the difficulties encountered by students.

Along with the frontal organization of students' work in the classroom, such a collective form as group work of students is also used, in which the audience is divided into several groups performing the same or different tasks. Depending on this, a single and differentiated group work is distinguished, and in both cases it is closely and inextricably linked to the frontal and individual work of students. Research by H.Y. Limits and other scientists have shown that the optimal composition of groups is 5-7 people. For successful collaboration, it is necessary to recruit groups of students with

approximately the same academic performance and the same pace of work. The composition of these groups is non-permanent and, as a rule, different in different subjects, determined by the students themselves, the teacher only adjusts it, taking into account the relationship between students.

Group work of students can be used to solve almost all major didactic problems: solving problems and exercises, consolidating and repeating, studying new material. As with individual learning, independent work of students is organized in groups, but the performance of differentiated group tasks teaches

According to psychologists, it is a prerequisite for the formation of correct concepts, as it allows you to get rid of subjectivity.

Frontal, group and individual work of students contributes to the implementation of educational and educational tasks in different ways. Therefore, it is necessary to have a rational combination of them, a reasonable and thoughtful choice of a particular form by the teacher, taking into account the peculiarities of the subject, the content of the material under study, teaching methods, the peculiarities of the class and individual students.

To involve everyone, you need to develop and improve your organizational skills to prepare a kind of lesson scenario.

Thirdly, the lesson should be provided with means of learning, Relevant tasks to be solved.

The means of training means everything material (technical and non-technical) that assists in the organization and conduct of the educational process.

So, the effectiveness of the educational process largely depends on the teacher's ability to organize the lesson correctly and competently choose a particular form of lesson.

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